

Substitution reactions of ligand bridged dinuclear complexes of cobalt(III) and chromium(III)

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Manuscript received 12 October 2006, accepted 2 November 2006

Abstract : This review encompasses the substitution reactions of various single and multiple bridged cobalt(III) and chromium(III) complexes. The reactions have been categorized with various bridging ligands, like oxo, peroxy, superoxy, hydroxo, cyano, carbonato, sulphato, amido etc. ligands. Reactions have usually been made in aqueous and basic media. In multiple bridged complexes, bridge cleavage generally takes place in a consecutive manner, although in a few cases simultaneous rupture of multiple bridges takes place. The nature of substitution depends both on the nature of substrate and also on the nature of the medium. In view of above observations, a review encompassing the substitutional activities of multinuclear cobalt(III) and chromium(III) complexes seems worth undertaking and an attempt to that direction have been taken up.

Keywords : Substitution reactions, bridged complex, dinuclear complex, cobalt(III), chromium(III).

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Ligand abbreviations :

bigH	biguanide, (NH ₂ C(NH)NH.C(NH)NH ₂)
cyclam	1,4,8,11-tetraazacyclotetradecane
dien	diethylenetriamine
dmap	dimethyl aminopyridine
en	ethylenediamine
etbigH	ethylenebisbiguanide
et ₂ dte	diethyldithiocarbamate
nta	nitrilotriacetate
phen	o-phenanthroline

tach	1,3,5-triaminocyclohexane
tacn	1,4,7-triazacyclononane, [9] one N ₃
tn	triethylenediamine
tmpa	tris(2-pyridylmethyl)amine
tren	triaminotriethylamine
trien	triethylenetetraamine : 1,4,7,10-tetraazadecane

1. Introduction

Studies on the reaction mechanisms of substitution reactions of coordination complexes were mostly made with mononuclear transition metal complexes. After elucidation of a reasonably clear picture for mononuclear complexes, attention was directed towards bi- and multinuclear complexes. The study is important as it can help in understanding of oxygen coordination and bridged structures are helpful for the elucidation of the structures of intermediates formed in substitution, electron transfer and other processes. Cobalt(III) complexes are studied most extensively. In many cases leaving group reactivity orders seem similar to mononuclear complexes¹. Apart from cobalt(III), a number of studies on the bridged chromium(III) complexes have also been made. However, studies on other metal ions as

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rhodium(III), osmium(III), ruthenium(II,III) etc. are scarce and only a few studies on these complexes have appeared in the literature². Molybdenum(IV,V) complexes have been investigated in detail, although their reactions are fast and stopped-flow technique is required to follow them³. In this review, we have presented a comparative account of the mechanisms of reactions of bridged complexes of cobalt(III) and chromium(III) ions. A number of studies have been made on these complexes, but they do not show uniformity in their rate laws. Redox and photochemical reactions have been kept outside the purview of the present review. Complex ions are arranged in the order of single bridged to bi- and tri-bridged complexes and from simple complexes to a more complicated one. An overall account of the mechanisms of these complexes has been presented in the following pages.

2. Single bridged cobalt(III) complexes

In this category most of the investigations were carried out with oxo-, superoxo- and peroxo-bridged complexes and a few with other bridging groups like hydroxo, carbonato and cyanido radicals. Acid-catalyzed reactions were preferred one. Role of incoming groups has also been investigated in a few cases. Table 1 presents these bridged complexes along with predicted rate laws and the medium and other conditions in which the reactions were carried out.

Green and Sykes investigated the dissociation of the superoxo bridged complex $\{(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2^-)^{5+}$ in presence of HNO_2 . Rate law is : $k_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{uncatal}} = k_{\text{HNO}_2}[\text{HNO}_2][\text{H}^+]^{-1}$. In presence of bromide ion, the reaction is catalyzed by Br^- , with a rate law, $k^{\text{Br}} = k_{\text{Br}}K_{\text{IP}}[\text{Br}^-][\text{HNO}_2] + K_{\text{IP}}[\text{Br}^-]$ and the product is aquapentaammine complex. Chloride is much less effective as a catalyst⁴.

Peroxo-bridged complexes, which are regarded as models for biological oxygen carriers, are investigated in maximum number. Di-pentaamminecobalt(III) complex undergoes protonation before rate determining dissociation⁵. Rate constant for unprotonated form (25° , 84 s^{-1} , $\Delta H^\ddagger 21.7 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger 36 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) is 1000 times greater than the protonated form (0.084 s^{-1} , $\Delta H^\ddagger 25 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger 36 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$). $\{(\text{NO}_2)\text{en}_2\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2^-)^{2+}$ ⁶ and $\{(\text{NH}_3)\text{en}_2\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2^-)^{4+}$ ⁷ also undergoes bridge cleavage after protonation in an equilibrium step^{6,7}. The reaction proceeds in two steps (i and ii). At 25° , k_1 and k_2 are $7.46, 0.405 \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\Delta H_1^\ddagger, \Delta H_2^\ddagger, 66.9, 85.4 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_1^\ddagger, \Delta S_2^\ddagger$ are $-2.9 \pm 4.2, 33.5 \pm 7.1 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. Bridge rupture of the cyclam complex, $\{(\text{cyclam})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2^-)^{4+}$ takes place in acid medium in a straight way depending on the acid concentration⁶. Rates of oxidation and reduction approach limiting behaviour, which is attributed to rate determining homolytic dissociation of peroxo complex. However, for the complex $\{(\text{NH}_3)(\text{tren})\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2^-)^{4+}$

Table 1. Single bridged cobalt(III) complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	Medium and other conditions	Rate law	Refs.
	$\text{O}_2^-, \text{O}_2^{2-}, \text{O}_2\text{H}^+$ bridges :			
1.	$\{(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2^-)^{5+}$	$[\text{HNO}_2] = (0.43\text{--}1.3) \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$ $[\text{H}^+] = 0.07\text{--}0.3 \text{ M}$	$k_{\text{obs}} = k_{\text{HNO}_2}[\text{HNO}_2]^{2+}[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$	4
2.	$\{(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2^-)^{4+}$	$I = 0.1 \text{ M LiClO}_4; [\text{H}^+] = 5 \times 10^{-3}\text{--}0.1 \text{ M}$	$k_{\text{obs}} = kK([\text{H}^+] + K)^{-1}$	5
3.	$\{(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2\text{H}^+)^{5+}$	$I = 0.1 \text{ M LiClO}_4; [\text{H}^+] = 5 \times 10^{-3}\text{--}0.1 \text{ M}$	Slow decomposition	5
4.	$\{(\text{NO}_2)\text{en}_2\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2^-)^{2+}$	Acidic medium	$k_{i(\text{obs})} = k_1K_1[\text{H}^+]/(1 + K_1[\text{H}^+]);$ $i = 1 \text{ or } 2$	6
5.	$\{(\text{cyclam})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2^-)^{4+}$	Acidic medium	$k_{i(\text{obs})} = k_1K_1[\text{H}^+]/(1 + K_1[\text{H}^+]);$ $i = 1 \text{ or } 2$	6
6.	$\{(\text{NH}_3)\text{en}_2\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2^-)$	$I = 0.1 \text{ M NaClO}_4; \text{temp.} = 15^\circ\text{--}25^\circ$	Two reactions take place simultaneously	7
7.	$\{(\text{NH}_3)(\text{tren})\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-O}_2^-)^{4+}$	$I = 0.35 \text{ M KCl}; \text{no pH dependency}$	$k_{\text{obs}} = k[\text{H}^+]$	8,9
	OH^- and other bridges :			
8a.	$\{(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-OH})^{5+}$	$I = 2.0 \text{ M LiClO}_4$	$k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k_1[\text{H}^+]$	10
8b.	$\{(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-OH})^{5+}$	with Y (Y = Cl^- , MeSO_3); $[\text{H}^+] = 10^{-4}\text{--}1.0 \text{ M}$	$k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k_1[\text{H}^+] + k_2[\text{H}^+][\text{Y}^-] + k_3[\text{H}^+][\text{Y}^-] \times (1 + k_4[\text{Y}^-])^{-1}$	11
9.	$\{(\text{NC})_5\text{Co}, \text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\}(\mu\text{-CN})$	$I = 0.5 \text{ M}; \text{Co}(\text{CN})_5^{3-}$ catalyzed	$k_{\text{obs}} = (k/2)[\text{complex}][\text{Catl.}][\text{CN}^-]$	12
10.	$\{(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-CO}_3)^{4+}$	Facile hydrolysis; no C ₀ -O bond cleavage		13
11.	$\{(\text{nta})(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Co}\}_2(\mu\text{-OH})$	Acid-dissociation below pH ~ 2.0		14

$O_2^-)^{4+}$ bridge cleavage takes place with redox reaction^{8,9}. At 25°, $I = 0.35 M$ KCl, $k_{obs} = 2 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$. Observed rate constant depends on acid concentration.

In all these oxo, superoxo and peroxo bridged complexes, bridge cleavage reaction proceeds through acid-catalyzed pathways only; there being no acid-independent path, although a pre-equilibrium between protonated and non-protonated species may establish before the bridge cleavage reaction operates in some cases.

Two studies have been made on the μ -hydroxo-dipentaamminecobalt(III) complex ion^{10,11}. Both the studies indicate acid-independent as well as acid-dependent pathways like the mononuclear complex. Nevertheless, one study indicates a first-order dependence on acid-concentration, but the other one indicates a pathway depending on the second power of acid-concentration in addition to acid-free and acid-dependent pathways.

Bridge cleavage reaction of the cyanide bridged complex $[(NC)_5Co-CN-Co(NH_3)_5]$ with cyanide ion is $[Co(CN)_5]^{3-}$ catalyzed¹². The carbonato complex $\{(NH_3)_5Co\}_2(\mu-CO_3)^{4+}$ undergoes facile acid hydrolysis to two moles of $[Co(NH_3)_5(H_2O)]^{3+} + CO_2$ ¹³. The reaction proceeds without Co-O bond fission. Reactions of these cyanide and carbonato bridged complexes do not share any common pattern with other oxo and hydroxo bridged complexes. The complex species $\{(nta)(H_2O)Co\}_2(\mu-OH)$ undergoes bridge cleavage below pH ~ 2 , via both acid-dependent and acid-independent pathways¹⁴. All the three hydroxide bridged complexes indicate a common mechanism that proceeds through acid-dependent as well as acid-independent pathways; a difference from other forms of oxygen bridged complexes which indicates only the acid-dependent pathway.

3. Double bridged cobalt(III) complexes

Double bridged complexes are far more numerous than single bridged complexes. These are more stable and availability of a large number of such complexes makes their study interesting. The bridging ligands may be same or of two different types. Table 2 records these complexes along with their bridge rupture rate laws in acidic medium.

Dihydroxo bridged complexes :

Ten complexes in this category have been studied. Tetraammine cobalt(III) dimer shows a two-step mechanism for its acid-catalyzed bridge cleavage in perchloric

acid medium. Mechanism proposed : opening of one of the hydroxide bridge by the assistance of H^+ , thus forming a single bridged intermediate. At 25°, $k_1 = 1.2 \times 10^{-3} mol^{-1} s^{-1}$; $k_1/k_2K = 0.57 \pm 0.05 mol^{-1}$ ¹⁵. But the aquatrimmine dimer indicates a straight away dependency on acid-concentration, with formation of the protonated reactive species¹⁶. Two studies have been made with $\{Coen_2\}_2 \cdot \mu(OH)_2^{4+}$. First bridge cleavage takes place with the formation of single bridged intermediate^{17,18}. However, in hydrochloric acid and sulfuric acid media, whose anions are potential ligands, there is some anation as well as aquation and bridge cleavage¹⁸.

In presence of perchloric and nitric acids, the bridge cleavage reaction of the complex ion $\{(bigH)_2Co\} \cdot \mu(OH)_2^{4+}$ proceeds only through acid-catalyzed path¹⁹. Rupture of first bridge is rate determining while breakage of the second bridge is fast. Rate equations, rate constants and activation parameters ($\Delta H^\ddagger 44.3 \pm 3.3 kJ mol^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger -188 \pm 18 JK^{-1} mol^{-1}$) are similar in presence of both perchloric and nitric acids. Acid aquation of the bis-oxalato-di- μ -hydroxo complex $\{(C_2O_4)_2Co\}_2(\mu-(OH)_2)^{4-}$ involves bridge fission to give di-oxalatoaquocobaltate(III) previous to electron transfer en-route to the final cobalt(III) product²⁰ (see Table 2 for rate law and other reaction conditions) (with $R = 0.5$, $10^4 k_1 = 5.42 \pm 0.11 s^{-1}$; $R = 1.0$, $10^4 k_1 = 24.5 \pm 0.6 s^{-1}$).

A study on the acid-catalyzed bridge cleavage reaction of the complex ion, $[(nta)Co-\mu(OH)_2-Co(nta)]^{2-}$ has revealed the presence of two isomers in solution with different reactivities. The rate constant of the slower reacting isomer is $1.6 \times 10^{-3} s^{-1}$, at least 200 times less than that for the faster reacting species. The same complex on being investigated more intensively indicated that the reaction proceeds via two pathways. The rate law for each step is similar²¹. Another study in basic solution in presence of pyridine and dmap indicated that the complex species equilibrate with single bridged species after rupture of one bridge and this single bridged species reacts with these incoming ligands. $k'(py) = 6.8 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$, $k''_{(dmap)} = 8.4 \times 10^{-2} s^{-1}$ ²².

A number of workers have investigated the reactions of $\{en_2Co\}_2 \cdot (\mu-O_2, OH)^{3+}$ ²³⁻²⁵. Except one, all of them obtained the same rate law. $\{(trien)Co\}_2 \cdot \mu(O_2, OH)^{3+}$ also gives the same rate law. At 25°, $k =$

Table 2. Double bridged cobalt(III) complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	Medium and other conditions	Rate law	Refs.
Dihydroxo complexes :				
1.	$\{(NH_3)_4Co\}_2(\mu-OH)_2^{4+}$	25°	$k_{obs} = k_1[H^+](1 + k_{-1}/k_2K)^{-1}[H^+]^{-1}$	15
2.	$\{(NH_3)_3(H_2O)Co\}_2(\mu-OH)_2^{4+}$		$k_{obs} = k_1K[H^+]$	16
3.	$\{en_2Co\}_2(\mu-OH)_2^{4+}$	(a) 25°, 1.0 M NaClO ₄ ; HClO ₄ (b) 25°, I = 1.0 M NaNO ₃ ; 2.43 × 10 ⁻³ M NaOH	$k_1(app.) = (C_{10} + C_{11}[H^+])/(1 + K_1[H^+]); k_2(app.) = \{C_{21}[H^+] + C_{22}[H^+]^2\}/(1 + K_2[H^+]);$ $k_3 = (C_{30} + C_{31}[OH^-])/(1 + K_3[OH^-])$	17
4.	$\{en_2Co\}_2(\mu-OH)_2^{4+}$	(a) 35°, 1.0 M NaClO ₄ ; HNO ₃ , HClO ₄ medium (b) 35°, 1.0 M NaClO ₄ ; H ₂ SO ₄ , HCl medium	$k_{obs} = k_0 + (a[H^+])/(1 + b[H^+]);$ Single bridge intermediate formation with same rate law	18
5.	$\{(bigH)_2Co\}_2(\mu-OH)_2^{4+}$	42-60°; I = 1.0 M NaClO ₄ , HClO ₄ , HNO ₃ , [H ⁺] = 0.3-1.0 M	$k_{obs} = k[H^+]$	19
6.	$\{(C_2O_4)_2Co\}_2(\mu-OH)_2^{4-}$	35°, 1.0 M NaClO ₄ ; pH 3.5-4.6	$k_{obs} = k_1(k_2 + k_3[RO_2^-])/(k_{-1} + k_2 + k_3)[RCOO^-]$, simplified form is : $k_{obs} = k_1 - a/[RCOO^-]$	20
7.	$\{nta.Co\}_2(\mu-OH)_2^{2-}$	35°. Recn. $\mu(OH)_2^{2-} \xrightleftharpoons[k_{-1}]{k_1} \mu(OH^-) \xrightarrow{k_2} Co(nta)(OH)_2$ (slow reaction)	$k_{obs} = a[H^+]^2/(b + [H^+])$ a = k ₁ = 0.131, b = 0.011 = k ₋₁ /k ₂	21
8.	$\{nta.Co\}_2(\mu-OH)_2^{2-}$	Different mechanism; larger reaction rate	$k_{obs} = kK[H^+]^2/(1 + k[H^+])$	21
9.	$\{nta.Co\}_2(\mu-OH)_2^{2-}$	Bridge cleavage in basic solution with py and dmap		22
Other bridging complexes :				
10.	$\{en_2.Co\}_2(\mu-O_2,OH^-)^{5+}$	25°, Acid medium; I = 0.2 M KCl	$k_{obs} = k[H^+]/([H^+] + K_a)$	23
11.	$\{(trien)Co\}_2(\mu-O_2,OH^-)^{3+}$	25°, [H ⁺] = 0.1 M; I = 0.2 N NaClO ₄	$k_{obs} = k[H^+]/([H^+] + K_a)$	24
12.	$\{(L)Co\}_2(\mu-O_2,OH^-)^{5+}$ L = en ₂ , tren, trien	20°, [H ⁺] = 0.01 M	$k_{obs} = k[H^+]$	25
13.	$\{(NH_3)_4Co\}_2(\mu-OH^-,NH_2)^{4+}$	25°, H ⁺ , Br ⁻ catalyzed	$k_{obs} = k[H^+][Br^-] + k_2[Br^-] + k_b$ (k _b = back recn.)	26
14.	$\{(NH_3)_4Co\}_2(\mu-OH^-,NH_2)^{4+}$	25°, H ⁺ , NCS ⁻ catalyzed	$k_{obs} = k_1[H^+][NCS^-] + k_2[NCS^-]$	27
15.	$(NH_3)_4Co(\mu-OH^-,NH_2)Co(H_2O)_4^{4+}$	25°-41.5°, I = 0.5 M, [H ⁺] = 0.048-0.385 M	$k_{obs} = k_1[H^+] + k_2$	28
16.	$\{(NH_3)_4Co\}_2(\mu-NH_2,SeO_4^-)$	25°, I = 2.0 M NaClO ₄	$k_{obs} = k_1[H^+] + k_0$	30
17.	$\{(NH_3)_2(CO_3)Co\}_2(\mu-(CO_3)^{2-})$	40°, [H ⁺] = 0.1-2.0 M; I = 2.0 M NaClO ₄	$k_{obs}^f = k_1^f[H^+] + k_2^f[H^+]; k_{obs}^s = k_1^s[H^+] + k_2^s$ (f = fast, s = slow)	29
18.	$\{tren.(NH_3)Co\}_2(\mu-O_2,tren)^{4+}$	25°, bond rupture by [H ⁺] catalysis; basic 'tren' is replaced by OH ⁻ , bridge	$k_{obs} = k[H^+]$	31
19.	$\{et(bigH)_2Co\}_2(\mu-et(bigH))^6+$	70°, [H ⁺] catalyzed	$k_{obs} = k_1[H^+] + k_2$	32
20.	$\{et(dtc)_2Co\}_2(\mu-et(dtc))$	25°, Recn. with DTO in CH ₂ Cl ₂	$k_{obs} = k_1 + k_2[DTO]; k_2 \gg k_1$	33
21.	$\{et(dtc)_2Co\}_2(\mu-et(dtc))$	25°, Recn. with en in CH ₂ Cl ₂	$k_{obs} = (k_1 + K_a[S]) = k_1K_c[CH_3OH] + k_1K_b[en]/k_{-1}$	34
22.	$(en)_2.Co(\mu-p_2CO_2)Fe(CN)_5^-$	Salt-effect studies		35

0.133 ± 0.012 s⁻¹ and K_a = 0.064²⁴. Aquation of the complex species {L.Co}₂(μ-O₂,OH⁻)³⁺, where L = trien, tren or en₂ was investigated by stopped-flow method. The product is cobalt(II) and protonated L. All

the O₂ are released in the process. At 293 K and pH = 2.0, k lies between 10⁻³ to 10⁻¹ s⁻¹ ²⁵. All these 'amine' complexes react in same fashion. Bromide²⁶ and thiocyanate²⁷ catalyzed bridge cleavage of {(NH₃)₄Co}₂.

$\mu(\text{OH}^-, \text{NH}_2^-)^{4+}$ indicated both acid-dependent and acid-independent paths. However, both the paths are also dependent on catalyst concentration. $(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{Co}-\mu(\text{OH}^-, \text{NH}_2^-)\cdot\text{Co}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4^{4+}$ shows acid-dependent and acid-free paths²⁸. The di- μ -carbonato complex $\{(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{CO}_3)\text{Co}\}_2\cdot\mu(\text{CO}_3)_2^{2-}$ decarboxylate with C-O bond rupture, leaving the oxygen bridges intact²⁹. The product $\{(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2\text{Co}\}_2\cdot\mu(\text{OH})_2^{4+}$ undergoes both water-induced and acid-catalyzed bridge cleavage reactions in two successive steps, ultimately forming *cis*- $\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3^{3+}$. At 40° C $\{I = 2.0 \text{ M NaClO}_4, [\text{H}^+] = 0.1-2.0 \text{ M}\}$, $k_{\text{fast}} = (2.20 \pm 0.18) \times 10^{-4} + 3.7 \times 10^{-4} [\text{H}^+]$ and $k_{\text{slow}} = 2.90 \times 10^{-5} + 11.85 \times 10^{-5} [\text{H}^+]$ ²⁹.

The selenito bridged complex $\{(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{Co}\}_2\cdot\mu\{\text{NH}_2^-, \text{SeO}_4^{2-}\}^{3+}$ at 25° ($I = 2.0 \text{ M NaClO}_4$) gives $\Delta H^\ddagger = 68.5 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger = -126 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ ³⁰.

A few other dinuclear, dibridged complexes (Table 2, No. 18-22) have been investigated where bridging bond rupture usually proceeds with reagent-dependent and reagent-free paths³¹⁻³⁵.

4. Triple bridged cobalt(III) complexes

All the studies in this category was made with trihydroxide bridged complexes, except one, which has one amide and two hydroxide bridges. Table 3 presents these complexes along with their rate laws. Kinetic studies were made mostly for rupture of the first bridge. In all these complexes in presence of H^+ ion, an equilibrium sets up between the non-protonated and the protonated species. The protonated species undergoes bridge cleavage reaction. Acid-catalyzed bridge cleavage for the trihydroxide bridged complex $\{(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Co}\}_2\cdot\mu(\text{OH}^-)_3^{3+}$ is quite fast and measured by stopped-flow technique. For the first bridge cleavage step (25°, $I = 1.0 \text{ M NaClO}_4$), $k_a = 4.22 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$; $\Delta H^\ddagger = 46.8 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$; $\Delta S^\ddagger = 76.5 \text{ JK mol}^{-1}$ ³⁶. Other rate and activation

parameters are given thereip. Another series of complex of the general formula $\{(\text{N}_3)\text{Co}\}_2\cdot\mu(\text{OH}^-)_3^{3+}$, where $\text{N}_3 = \text{N}(\text{NH}_3)_3$, dien or *cis-cis*-1,3,5-triaminocyclohexane have been investigated for acid catalysis³⁸. The reactions are :

This reaction is rapid, takes place in two steps. First one being 100 times faster than the second one ($t_{1/2}$ for first steps are 0.02, 0.03, 0.025 seconds respectively at $I = 1.0 \text{ M}$, 20°, pH 0, $t_{1/2}$ for 2nd step is 4-9 s for all.

The equilibrium kinetics of first hydroxo bridge cleavage of triply bridged complexes $\{(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Co}\}_2\cdot\mu(\text{OH})_3^{3+}$ (I) and $\{(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Co}\}_2\cdot\mu(\text{NH}_2^-, (\text{OH}^-)_2)^{3+}$ (II) have been studied at $I = 1.0 \text{ M LiClO}_4$, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.01-0.5 \text{ M}$. At 25° for I, $K_p = 1.51 \text{ L mol}^{-1}$, $k_1 = 1.86 \times 10^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_{-1} = 6.62 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ and for II, $K_p < 0.05 \text{ L mol}^{-1}$, $k_2 K_p = 1.01 \text{ L mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_{-2} = 1.96 \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Activation parameters for k_1 , k_{-1} , $k_2 K_p$, k_{-2} are; $\Delta H^\ddagger = 99, 95, 52$ and 121 kJ mol^{-1} ; $\Delta S^\ddagger = 69, 32, -71, 128 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively³⁷. The triple hydroxide bridged complex $\{(1,4,7\text{-triazacyclononane})\text{Co}\}_2\cdot\mu(\text{OH})_3$ at 20° and $I = 1.0 \text{ M LiClO}_4$ shows simple acid-dependent and acid-independent paths³⁹.

Thus the nature of bridge cleavage of these triple bridged complexes are almost alike.

5. Single bridged chromium(III) complexes

Dinuclear chromium(III) complexes undergo bridge cleavage both in acid as well as in basic mediums. Both the reaction types were investigated by the workers. Oxo-, peroxo- and hydroxo-bridged complexes belong

Table 3. Triple bridged cobalt(III) complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	Medium and other conditions	Rate law	Refs.
1.	$\{(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Co}\}_2\cdot\mu(\text{OH})_3^{3+}$	$I = 1.0 \text{ M}$	First bridge cleavage only	36
2.	$\{(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Co}\}_2\cdot\mu(\text{OH})_3^{3+}$	$[\text{H}^+] = 0.01-0.50 \text{ M}$ $I = 1.0 \text{ M (LiClO}_4)$	$k_{\text{obs}} = \{k_1 K_p [\text{H}^+] / (1 + K_p [\text{H}^+])\} + k_1$	37
3.	$\{\text{N}_3\cdot\text{Co}\}_2\cdot\mu(\text{OH})_3^{3+}$ N = $(\text{NH}_3)_3$, dien, tach-trial. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_9(\text{NH}_2)_3$	20°, $I = 1.0 \text{ M}$, pH ~0	$k_{\text{obs}} = a[\text{H}^+] / (1 + b[\text{H}^+])$	38
4.	$\{(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Co}\}_2\cdot\mu(\text{NH}_2, \text{OH}, \text{OH})^{3+}$	25°; $I = 1.0 \text{ M LiClO}_4$, $[\text{H}^+] = 0.01-0.5 \text{ M}$	$k_{\text{obs}} = k_2 K_p [\text{H}^+] + k_2$	37
5.	$\{(1,4,7\text{-triazacyclononane})\text{Co}\}_2\cdot\mu(\text{OH})_3$	20°; $I = 1.0 \text{ M LiClO}_4$	$k_{\text{obs}} = a[\text{H}^+] + b$	39

Table 4. Single bridged chromium(III) complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	Medium and other conditions	Rate law	Refs.
1.	$\{(H_2O)_5Cr\}_2 \cdot \mu-(O^{2-})^{4+}$	$[H^+] = 0.1-1.0 M HClO_4, I = 1.0 M NaClO_4$	$k_{obs} = k_0 + k_1[H^+]$	40
2.	$\{(NH_3)_5Cr\}_2 \cdot \mu-(OH)^{5+}$	$[H^+] = 0.1-1.0 M HClO_4$ $I = 1.0 M NaClO_4$	$k_{obs} = k[\text{complex}]$; rate independent of H^+	41
3.	$[(NH_3)_5Cr(NH_3)_4X]$ ($X = H_2O, Cl^-$)	$[H^+] = 0.1-1.0 M HClO_4$ $I = 1.0 M NaClO_4$	$k_{obs} = k[\text{complex}]$; rate independent of H^+	41
4.	$\{(\text{tmpa})CrCl\}_2 \cdot \mu-(O)^{2+}$ $\{(\text{tmpa})Cr\}_2 \cdot \mu-(O,F)^{3+}$	25° , pH 4.16; biphasic plot for Cl complex	$k_{obs} = k$	42
5.	$\{(\text{tmpa})LCr\}_2 \cdot \mu-(O)^{2+}$ $L = NCS^-, NCO^-, CN^-, NCS_2^-, N_3^-$	$40^\circ, I = 1.0 M LiClO_4$	$k = k_0 + k_1[OH^-]$	45
6.	$\{(NH_3)_5Cr\}_2 \cdot \mu-(O)^{4+}$	$NH_3(aq) 1.0 M; I = 0.5 M LiClO_4$	$k = k_0 + k_1[OH^-]$	46
7.	$\{(\text{tmpa})LCr\}_2 \cdot \mu-(O)^{2+}$ $L = NCS_2^-, N_3^-$	$I = 1.0 M$; excess OH^-	$k_{obs} = \frac{k_0 + k_b Q_p [OH^-]}{(1 + Q_p [OH^-])}$	43,44
8.	$[(NH_3)_5Cr \cdot \mu-(OH)(NH_3)_4NCS]^{4+}$	25° , formation studies with excess SCN^-	$k = k_1 + k_2[NCS^-]$	48

to preferred category. Table 4 records these complexes along with their general conditions of reactions and rate laws. Acid-catalyzed reaction of $\{(H_2O)_5Cr\}_2 \cdot \mu-(O)^{4+}$ gives $Cr(H_2O)_6^{3+}$ as the sole product⁴⁰. At 298.2 K, $10^5 k_0 = 5.0 s^{-1}$, $10^3 k_1 = 1.61 dm^3 mol^{-1} s^{-1}$, ΔH_0^\ddagger , ΔH_1^\ddagger are 92, 54 kJ mol⁻¹; ΔS_0^\ddagger , ΔS_1^\ddagger are 21 and -117 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively. In 0.1-1.0 M HClO₄, three complexes $\{(NH_3)_5Cr\}_2 \cdot \mu-(OH)^{5+}$ (I), $(NH_3)_5Cr(\mu-OH)Cr(NH_3)_4(H_2O)^{5+}$ (II) and $\{(NH_3)_5Cr(OH^-)Cr(NH_3)_4Cl\}^{4+}$ (III) undergo bridge cleavage with a rate constant independent of [acid]⁴¹. At 55°, $I = 1.0 M NaClO_4$, $k_I = 7.6 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$, $k_{II} = 11.8 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$ and at 65°, $k_{III} = 4.0 \times 10^{-4} s^{-1}$. ΔH^\ddagger for all three complexes is 117 kJ mol⁻¹. $\{(\text{tmpa})CrCl\}_2 \cdot \mu-(O)^{2+}$ also indicates two acid-independent reaction paths. $10 k_{fast} = 1.6 s^{-1}$, $10^2 k_{slow} = 0.696 s^{-1}$ ⁴².

Thus rupture of bridging bond of binuclear chromium(III) complexes takes place by acid-free paths primarily, although in some complexes acid-dependent path might have been involved.

A few reactions that have been carried out in basic medium, indicate both base-dependent and base-independent pathways^{43,44}. $\{(\text{tmpa})LCr\}_2 \cdot \mu-(O)^{2+}$, where $L = NCS^-, NCO^-, CN^-$ gives a rate law, $k_{obs} = k_0 + k_1 [OH^-]$ (at 40°, $I = 1.0 M LiClO_4$). For $L = NCO^-$, k_0 and k_1 are $4.1 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$ and $1.07 \times 10^{-3} mol^{-1} s^{-1}$. For $L = CN^-$, k_0 and k_1 are $6.8 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$, $k_{OH} = 4.17 \times 10^{-4} mol^{-1} s^{-1}$. At 45°, 0.1 M NaOH, the

NCS⁻ complex undergoes rapid conversion to hydroxo intermediate prior to bridge cleavage⁴⁵. Sensitivity of base hydrolyses rates to the L⁻ leaving group is reflected as :

Base hydrolysis of the ion $\{(NH_3)_5Cr\}_2 \cdot \mu-(O)^{4+}$ is independent of the effect of OH⁻, Cl⁻, F⁻ ions. ΔH^\ddagger 70 kJ mol⁻¹; ΔS^\ddagger -41.8 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹⁴⁶. Base hydrolysis reactions of $\{Cr(\text{tmpa})(NCS_2)\}_2 \cdot \mu-(O)^{2+}$ and $\{Cr(\text{tmpa})(N_3)\}_2 \cdot \mu-(O)^{2+}$ follow a pseudo-first order relationship⁴³.

Bridge-formation reactions are reverse of bridge-rupture processes. These reactions are included here for a better understanding of both the processes. Oxidation of $Cr(H_2O)_6^{2+}$ by benzoquinone in acidic solution gives two bridged species $[(H_2O)_4Cr \cdot \mu(OH, HQ)Cr(H_2O)_4]^{4+}$ (major) and $[(H_2O)_5Cr \cdot O \cdot Cr(H_2O)_5]^{4+}$ (minor). The HQ complex aquates too slowly to be the precursor of the oxo-bridged dimer⁴⁷. Mechanism proposed is : oxidation by protonated benzoquinone followed by rapid loss of hydroquinone. A study on the formation of $[(NH_3)_5Cr \cdot \mu(OH) \cdot Cr(NH_3)_4 \cdot NCS]^{4+}$ by the reaction of SCN^- and *cis*- $[(NH_3)_5Cr \cdot OH \cdot Cr(NH_3)_4(H_2O)]^{5+}$ has been carried out. The reaction indicates two paths. at 25° k for the NCS⁻ independent path is $3.44 \times 10^{-5} s^{-1}$ and for the NCS⁻ dependent path is $10.1 \times 10^{-5} L mol^{-1} s^{-1}$ ⁴⁸.

6. Double bridged chromium(III) complexes

A variety of reactions including acid and base catalyzed reactions, isomerization and dimerization reactions etc., have been investigated for double bridged chromium(III) complexes. The complexes undertaken for investigation are listed in Table 5. Kinetics of the equilibrium between di- μ -hydroxo and μ -hydroxo dinuclear complex ions of the type,

have been investigated and at 274 K, $I = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[H^+] = 1.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $10^4 k_1 = 3.6 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $10^4 k_{-1} = 4.23 \text{ s}^{-1}$. ΔH_1^\ddagger and ΔH_{-1}^\ddagger are 82 and 86 kJ mol^{-1} respectively^{49a,b}. Acid-catalyzed bridge cleavage of the same complex $\{en_2Cr\}_2-\mu(OH)_2^{4+}$ was again investigated in 12 N HCl. The reaction leads to *cis*- $[Cren_2(H_2O)_2]^{3+}$ (43%), *cis*- $[Cren_2(H_2O)Cl]^{2+}$ (19%) and *cis*- $[Cren_2Cl_2]^+$ (38%)⁵⁰. The reaction involves a series of consecutive and parallel reactions. The first bridge cleavage yields $[Clen_2Cr(OH)Cren_2(H_2O)_4]^{4+}$

Table 5a. Double bridged chromium(III) complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	Medium and other conditions	Rate law	Refs.
1.	$\{en_2Cr\}_2-\mu(OH)_2^{4+}$	$[H^+] = 10^{-5}-1.0 \text{ M}$, $I = 1.0 \text{ M}$	$\text{Diol} = \frac{k_1}{k_{-1}} \text{ monool}$	49(a)
2.	$\{en_2Cr\}_2-\mu(OH)_2^{4+}$	Diol-monool equilibrium at 20° Aqueous soln. $I = 1.0 \text{ M NaClO}_4$	$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1[\text{diol}] - k_{-1}K_{a1}/(K_a + H^+) \times \text{monool}$	49(b)
3.	$\{en_2Cr\}_2-\mu(OH)_2^{4+}$	12 N HCl; 9–12 M HClO ₄	$\text{Diol} = \frac{k}{k'} \{en_2ClCr\}_2(OH)^{3+}$	50
4.	$\{en_2Cr\}_2-\mu(OH)_2^{4+}$	H ₂ SO ₄ medium; SO ₄ ²⁻ bridge formation	$k_{\text{obs}} = k[H^+]$	51
5.	$\{en_2Cr\}_2-\mu(OH_2)^{4+}$	$[H^+]$, with RCOOH (R = CH ₃ , H, H ₃ N ⁺ , CH ₂ , NH ₂ CH ₃)	-	52
6.	$\{pn_2Cr\}_2-\mu(OH_2)^{4+}$	0.01 M HClO ₄ , $I = 1.0 \text{ M NaClO}_4$ (pH ~ 5.0)	$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + k_{-1}$	53
7.	$\{phen\}_2Cr_2-\mu(OH)_2^{4+}$	Aq. HNO ₃ , $I = 1.0 \text{ M NaNO}_3$	$k_{\text{obs}} = k[H^+]$ [dimer]	54
8.	$\{phen\}_2Cr_2-\mu(OH)_2^{4+}$	$[H^+] = 0.1-1.0 \text{ M HNO}_3$, $I = 1.0 \text{ M NaNO}_3$, temp. 57–75°	$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + k_2[H^+]$	55
9.	$Cr_2(\text{etbigH})_3^{6+}$	Temp 40–60° $[HClO_4] = 0.3-0.7 \text{ M}$, $I = 1.0 \text{ M NaClO}_4$	$k_{\text{obs}} = k_1[H^+]$	32
10.	$(SCN)_4Cr-\mu(SCN)_2Ru(\text{bigH})_2^0$	Formation study, pH 4.0–6.1; 21–40° (K_1 , K_2 acid disso. const. of diaqua complex, k_2 rate of formation)	$k_{\text{obs}} = \frac{k_2 + K_1[H^+]}{[H^+]^2 + K_1[H^+] + K_1K_2}$	56
11.	$\{(H_2O)L_3Cr\}_2-\mu(OH)_2^{4+}$ L = tacn, fac (NH ₃) ₃	$I = 1.0 \text{ M NaClO}_4$ <i>cis</i> \rightleftharpoons <i>trans</i> 25°, pH 2–11	$K_n = k_n/k_{-n}$ (n = 1–3)	57

Table 5b. Reactions in basic medium

12.	$\{en_2Cr\}_2-\mu(OH^-, RCO_2)^{4+}$	Basic medium	Two stage reaction	58
13.	$\{en_2Cr\}_2-\mu(OH, RCO_2)Cr(\text{nta})^{4+}$	Basic medium	Two stage reaction	58
14.	$\{(t\text{mpa})Cr\}_2-\mu(OH)_2^{2+}$	0.1–1.0 M [OH ⁻], $I = 1.0 \text{ M NaOH/NaBr}$; biphasic reaction	$k_{\text{fast}} = k_0^f + k_{\text{OH}}^f [\text{OH}^-]$; $k_{\text{slow}} = k_0^s + k_{\text{OH}}^s [\text{OH}^-]$	59
15.	$\{t\text{mpa}Cr\}_2-\mu(O, RCO_2)^{3+}$ R = H, CH ₃ , CH ₂ Cl, C(CH ₃) ₃ etc.	Basic medium, 60°, $I = 1.0 \text{ M}$	$k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k_{\text{OH}} [\text{OH}^-]$, for R = H; $k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k_b Q_p [\text{OH}^-]/(1 + Q_p [\text{OH}^-])$, for R = others	60
16.	$\{t\text{mpa}Cr\}_2-\mu(O, \text{Ph.PO}_4)^{4+}$ $\{t\text{mpa}Cr\}_2-\mu(O, \text{CO}_3)^{2+}$	60°, $I = 1.0 \text{ M}$	$k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k_b Q_p [\text{OH}^-]/(1 + Q_p [\text{OH}^-])$	43

which then undergoes direct bridge cleavage by aquation and by anation and bridge cleavage takes place via the formation of $[\text{Clen}_2\text{Cr}(\text{OH})\text{Cren}_2\text{Cl}]^{3+}$. Kinetic data for bridge cleavage in perchloric and hydrochloric acids have been reported⁵⁰. The same complex, $\{\text{en}_2\text{Cr}\}_2-\mu(\text{OH})_2^{4+}$ in presence of sulfuric acid gives $\{\text{en}_2\text{Cr}\}_2-\mu(\text{OH}^-, \text{SO}_4^{2-})^{3-}$ complex. Sulfate ion occupies one of the bridge position replacing the OH^- bridge⁵¹. This complex ion with RCOOH ($\text{R} = \text{CH}_3, \text{H}, \text{H}_3\text{N}^+\text{CH}_2$ or NH_2CH_2) gives $\{\text{en}_2\text{Cr}\}_2-\mu(\text{OH}^-, \text{RCOO}^-)^{4+}$ ⁵². Kinetics of the equilibrium $\{(\text{LL})_2\text{Cr}\}_2^{4+} + \text{H}_2\text{O} \xrightleftharpoons[k_{-1}]{k_1} [(\text{LL})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{Cr}-\mu(\text{OH})\text{Cr}(\text{OH})(\text{LL})_2]^{4+}$ ($\text{LL} = 1,3\text{-pn}$) at 298.2 gives a rate constant $(k_1 + k_{-1}) = k_{\text{obs}} = 6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ⁵³. The complex ion $\{(\text{phen})_2\text{Cr}\}_2-\mu(\text{OH}_2)^{4+}$ investigated at an earlier date indicated acid-catalyzed path only for bridge cleavage in acid medium⁵⁴. At 60°, $k_{\text{obs}} = 9.9 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($I = 1.0 \text{ M NaNO}_3$), $\Delta H^\ddagger = 88 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^\ddagger = -45 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The same complex ion along with di-bridged $\mu\text{-}(\text{O}, \text{O})$ and $\mu\text{-}(\text{O}, \text{OH})$ complexes investigated on a later date indicated both acid-catalyzed and acid-free paths for bridge cleavage reactions⁵⁵. The di-bridged species $\mu\text{-}(\text{O}, \text{O})$ and $\mu\text{-}(\text{OH}, \text{O})$ in acid solution convert to the dihydroxo form. All these three complexes undergo aquation with a rate law, $k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + k_2 [\text{H}^+]$. Protonation of one of the bridging ligands results in its cleavage and on rupture of the first bridging ligand, the other one also breaks down simultaneously. At 75°, k_1 is $7.9 \pm 0.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $k_2 = 15.7 \pm 0.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. Activation parameters are, $\Delta H_1^\ddagger, \Delta H_2^\ddagger$ 77 ± 4, 48 ± 4 kJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta S_1^\ddagger, \Delta S_2^\ddagger$ -105 ± 12, -178 ± 14 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ respectively. All the three species indicate same rate and activation parameters.

The tetradentate ligand, ethylenebisbiguanide, forms a complex with chromium(III) ion as $[\text{Cr}_2(\text{etbigH})_3]^{6+}$, where the two chromium(III) ions are bonded by the wrapping of the ligand. This complex in acid solution undergoes bridge cleavage by acid-catalyzed path only. At 50°, k_{obs} is $6.4 \pm 0.2 \times 10^{-5} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, ΔH^\ddagger 79 ± 6 kJ mol⁻¹ and ΔS^\ddagger -84 ± 12 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹³². Formation of the thiocyanato bridged dinuclear complex $[(\text{SCN})_4\text{Cr}-\mu(\text{SCN})_2.\text{Ru}(\text{BigH})_2]^{10}$ by the reaction of $\text{Cr}(\text{SCN})_6^{3-}$ and $[\text{Ru}(\text{BigH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]^{3+}$ was investigated in the pH range 4.40–5.80 between 21–40°. The hydroxo aqua form of the ruthenium complex is reactive in this pH range. k_{obs} at 31° is $(2.57 \pm 0.05) \times 10^{-3}$

mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, ΔH^\ddagger 60 ± 2 kJ mol⁻¹ and ΔS^\ddagger -116 ± 10 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹⁵⁶. Kinetic investigations of the *cis-trans* isomerization of the dihydroxo bridged chromium(III) triamine dimers with facially coordinated ammonia or 1,4,7-triazacyclononane were carried out spectrophotometrically at $10^{-11} < [\text{H}^+] > 10^{-2} \text{ M HClO}_4$ at 25° in 1.0 M NaClO₄. The experiments demonstrate a direct *cis-trans* isomerization path for which the rate constants k_n and k_{-n} ($K_n = k_n/k_{-n}$, $n = 1-3$) were determined⁵⁷.

It is interesting to note here that cleavage of mono and dihydroxo bridged complexes of most of the inert metal ions like cobalt(III), rhodium(III) and iridium(III) are highly influenced by acid but that of chromium(III) complexes are usually little to none. Acid-free paths are more important for chromium(III) complexes.

Base catalyzed bridge cleavage of dinuclear complexes $\{[(\text{en})_2\text{Cr}]_2-\mu(\text{OH}^-, \text{RCO}_2^-)^{4+}$ and $[(\text{nta})\text{Cr}-\mu(\text{OH}^-, \text{RCO}_2^-)\text{Cren}_2]^-$ ($\text{R} = \text{H}, \text{CH}_3, \text{C}_2\text{H}_5$) occur in two stages (k_1 and k_2). k_1 varies with R, but k_2 is same for all⁵⁸. The reaction scheme may be presented as :

$\{(\text{phen})_2\text{Cr}\}_2-\mu(\text{OH})_2^{4+}$ in basic medium undergoes bridge cleavage independent of base concentration⁵⁵. At 60°, k is $15.82 \pm 0.08 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$, ΔH^\ddagger 43 ± 4 kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS^\ddagger -45 ± 6 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

Recently a number of base catalyzed rupture of bridging bonds in dibridged chromium(III) complexes, have been investigated by Holwerda *et al.* The complex ion $\{[(\text{tmpa})\text{Cr}]_2-\mu(\text{O})_2^{2+}$ follows a consecutive first order kinetics in 0.1–1.0 M $[\text{OH}^-]$ ($I = 1.0 \text{ M}$ (NaOH/NaBr)), with both fast (89%) and slow (11%) components exhibiting parallel pathways of zero (k_0^f and k_0^s , respectively) and first order (k_{OH}^f and k_{OH}^s , respectively) in OH^- ion. At 25°, the rate parameters are : $k_0^f = 3.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (ΔH^\ddagger 83 kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS^\ddagger -33 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹), $k_{\text{OH}}^f = 5.8 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (ΔH^\ddagger 94 kJ mol⁻¹, ΔS^\ddagger

$= +8.3 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$). $k_0^{\ddagger} = 4.7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($\Delta H^{\ddagger} 96 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^{\ddagger} -4.2 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) and $k_{\text{OH}}^{\ddagger} = 2.7 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$ ($\Delta H^{\ddagger} 117 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^{\ddagger} +59 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$). Mechanism has been proposed as aqua and hydroxide ion assisted Cr-O bond cleavage⁵⁹. Base-assisted hydrolysis of the dibridged complex, $\{(\text{tmpa})\text{Cr}\}_2\text{-}\mu(\text{O}, \text{RCOO})^{3+}$ indicated a rate equation as : $k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k_{\text{OH}}[\text{OH}^-]$. At 60° and $\text{R} = \text{H}$, k_0 is $2.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$, ΔH^{\ddagger} , ΔS^{\ddagger} are 83 JK and $-46 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. $k_{\text{OH}} = 6.84 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, ΔH^{\ddagger} , ΔS^{\ddagger} are 86 kJ and $-8 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively. All other species having $\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$, CH_2Cl , CHCl_2 , $\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2$ etc. have a rate law as : $k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k_{\text{OH}} \cdot Q_p \cdot [\text{OH}^-] / (1 + Q_p[\text{OH}^-])^{60}$. Complexes $\{(\text{tmpa})_2\text{Cr}\}_2\text{-}\mu(\text{O}, \text{PhPO}_4)^{4+}$ and $\{(\text{tmpa})_2\text{Cr}\}_2\text{-}\mu(\text{O}, \text{CO}_3)^{2+}$ follow a pseudo-first order relationship, $k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k_b \cdot Q_p \cdot [\text{OH}^-] / (1 + Q_p[\text{OH}^-])$ ($Q_p =$ ion-pair constant). The carbonato bridged complex (60° , $I = 1.0 \text{ M}$) gives rate parameters as : $k_b = (1.5 \pm 0.3) \times 10^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^{\ddagger} 61.2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^{\ddagger} -99 \pm 7 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$. $Q_p 3.8 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta H_0^{\ddagger} 67 \pm 2 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S_0^{\ddagger} 230 \pm 7 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ ⁴³.

From all these rate parameters, it appears that all the complexes follow essentially the same pathway. All the base catalyzed reactions indicate a two-term rate law, one dependent on base concentration and the other one is free of it. Unlike acid-assisted bridge cleavage reactions, the base-catalyzed pathways are more important than the non-catalyzed paths in all these base-catalyzed bridging bond cleavage reactions.

7. Triple bridged chromium(III) complexes

Triple bridged chromium(III) complexes are less in number and hence number of studies on these complexes are also limited (Table 6). All the studies were made for the first bridge cleavage reactions only. The complex ion $\{(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Cr}\}_2\text{-}\mu(\text{OH})_3^{3+}$ is hydrolyzed in

aqueous solution ($0.8 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) to *cis*-diol form with half-life 5-6 min ($k = 1.92 \times 10^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$). Hydrolysis is faster both in acidic and in basic solutions⁶¹. Kinetics of the acid-catalyzed decarboxylation of the species $\{\text{LCr}\}_2\text{-}\mu(\text{OH}^-)_2(\text{CO}_3^{2-})^{2+}$ ($\text{L} = 1,4,7\text{-triazacyclononane}$, [9] one N_3) proceeds both through acid-dependent and acid-independent paths. $k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k_1[\text{H}^+]$, k_0 , k_1 at 30° are $0.31 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$, $6.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$; ΔH^{\ddagger} , ΔS^{\ddagger} are 85.7 , 64.7 kJ mol^{-1} ; -48 , $-106 \text{ JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ respectively⁶². Decarboxylation of CO_3^{2-} bridge and bidentate CO_3^{2-} are accompanied by the same mechanism. Sulfate bridge cleavage of $\{(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3\text{Cr}\}_2\text{-}\mu[(\text{OH}^-)_2, \text{SO}_4^{2-}]^{2+}$ takes place with the rate law, $k_{\text{obs}} = k_1 + k_2[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$, $\Delta H^{\ddagger} 93 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ ⁶³.

Mechanisms of the triple bridged chromium(III) complexes are similar to their cobalt(III) counterparts. However, like mononuclear complexes these dinuclear triply bridged complexes are more labile than the corresponding cobalt(III) complexes.

8. Conclusion

In this review the work that has been presented, demonstrate mechanistic aspects of cobalt(III) and chromium(III) complexes having different types of bridging ligands connecting two metal centers. Mechanistic aspects of a reaction depend not only on the bridging ligands but also on the substrates present. Occasionally question has been raised if the complexes of cobalt(III) and chromium(III) have common mechanistic pathways⁶⁴. However, multinuclear complexes of cobalt(III) although usually react by catalyzed pathways, those of chromium(III) prefers non-catalyzed pathways or at least this is the more important pathway. Some new types of multinuclear complexes having metal-metal bonds have been synthesized recently⁶⁵. Mechanistic studies on such complexes are considered as potential field of investiga-

Table 6. Triple bridged chromium(III) complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	Medium and other conditions	Rate law	Refs.
1.	$\{(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{Cr}\}_2\text{-}\mu(\text{OH})_3^{3+}$	Neutral pH, $[\text{H}^+]$, $[\text{OH}^-]$; 0.8° ; converts to diol	$k_{\text{obs}} = k$; $k_{\text{obs}} = k[\text{H}^+]$ or $k[\text{OH}^-]$	61
2.	$\{([9] \text{ one } \text{N}_3)\text{Cr}\}_2\text{-}\mu\{(\text{OH})_2, \text{CO}_3^{2-}\}^{2+}$ (1,4,7-triazacyclononane)	HClO_4 , acid medium	$k_{\text{obs}} = k_0 + k_1[\text{H}^+]$	62
3.	$\{(\text{H}_2\text{O})_3\text{Cr}\}_2\text{-}\mu\{(\text{OH}^-)_2, (\text{SO}_4^{2-})\}^{2+}$	HClO_4 , acid medium	$k = k_1 + k'[\text{H}^+]^{-1}$	63

tion and may lay another impetus for studying these complexes.

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